

The Arch of Titus

By Gretel Rodriguez, Brown University

Entry tags: Roman Religions, Polytheistic, Ancient Mediterranean, Religious Group, Roman Religious Traditions, Archaeological monument, Religious Place, Monument, Cenotaph, Triumphal Arch, Rome

Honorific monument built in Rome to commemorate the death and apotheosis of the emperor Titus (reigned: 79-81 CE).

Date Range: 81 CE - 81 CE

Region: Rome

Region tags: Europe, Western Europe, Rome, Italy

City of Rome in the late first and early second centuries CE.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Pfanner, M. "Der Titusbogen." Mainz am Rhein: Philipp von Zabern, 1983.
- Source 2: Lehmann-Hartleben, K. "L'arco Di Tito." *Bullettino della Commissione Archeologica Comunale di Roma* 62 (1934): 89-122.
- Source 3: De Maria, S. *Gli archi onorari di Roma e dell'Italia romana*. Roma: L'Erma di Bretschneider, 1988: 287-89.

Notes: Torelli, Mario, "Culto imperiale e spazi urbani in età flavia: dai rilievi Hartwig all'arco di Tito." In *L'Urbs: espace urbain et histoire (1o. Siècle Av. J.c. - IIIa. Siècle Ap. J.c.)*, edited by P. Gros, 565-82. Roma: Ecole Française de Rome, 1987

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Elevation

Type of elevation

– Hill

Notes: The arch stands at the top of the elevation known as the Velia or the Velian Hill, which links the Forum to the West with the Colosseum Valley to the East and the Palatine Hill to the South.

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– Yes

↳ The structure has a definite shape

– Other [specify]: A traditional single-bayed archway structure. Dimensions: 14 x 6.20 meters at the base and 14.44 meters in elevation. De Maria, *Gli archi onorari di Roma e dell'Italia romana*. Roma: L'Erma di Bretschneider, 1988, p. 287

↳ One single feature

– Other [specify]: An arch structure spanning a road (Via Sacra)

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

↳ A group of features:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

Notes: This is the confluence of numerous religious and secular buildings and features, including the Via Sacra, the Arch, several temples, commercial structures and the Imperial Palace (Domus Flavia).

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

Notes: Not strictly speaking, but generally this area was loaded with religious/political/mythological meaning, being among the earliest urbanized spaces in the city of Rome.

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

– Yes

↳ Function:

– Memorial

Notes: The primary function is a cenotaph/memorial for the deceased emperor Titus. It however, had other symbolic and political functions associated with Titus' successor, Domitian.

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

Notes: In the Roman period the structure stood alone as a single commemorative feature. It was later incorporated into a medieval construction when it also functioned as a gateway to the Forum and Palatine areas. The monument was "freed" from the medieval additions during Valadier's reconstruction in the early 19th century.

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

– Collapsed

Notes: OTHER

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

– For economic reasons

– For political reasons

– Other [specify]: Large parts of the armature and attached decoration were destroyed when the monument was rebuilt as part of a medieval building.

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:

– Human-caused accident

– Natural phenomena

Notes: Possibly also affected by earthquakes, fire, and natural erosion.

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Yes

↳ In antiquity

– Periodically

Notes: Most ancient monuments were restored periodically. Arches in particular, have chambers in the attic and elsewhere within the structure to facilitate this process.

↳ In modernity

– Post-Renaissance

Notes: Again, see reconstruction as noted above: Giuseppe Valadier and Raffaele Stern, "Narrazione artistica dell'operato finora nel restauro dell'Arco di Tito letta nell'Accademia Romana di Archeologia." Rome: Stamperia de Romania, 1822.

– Renaissance

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: The monument was dedicated in honor of the deified emperor Titus, as expressed in the dedicatory inscription. The apotheosis of Titus is part of the decoration, appearing in the relief on the arch's vault.

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– Field doesn't know

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

↳ Type of feature

– Leveling of ground

– Clearing

– Other [specify]: Additional construction

Notes: The structure saddles the current road that leads from the Colosseum Valley to the Forum. In antiquity, it probably spanned the Via Sacra.

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– Yes

↳ Is it a cenotaph:

– Yes

↳ Body present:

– No

↳ Part of body present:

– No

↳ Does it commemorate a family/clan/group:

– Yes

Notes: Although strictly speaking this is a Senatorial dedication in honor of Titus, the monument also honors Titus' deified father Vespasian and his brother and successor, Domitian. Therefore, it expresses certain dynastic concerns regarding the Flavian clan.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: http://penelope.uchicago.edu/~grout/encyclopaedia_romana/romanurbs/archtitus.html

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.yu.edu/cis/activities/arch-of-titus>

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

↳ Type of excavation:

– Pre-modern

Notes: There have been several excavations at intervals between the nineteenth century and the present. The current state of the monument is the result of major a restoration carried out by Giuseppe Valadier and Raffaele Stern in the 1820s. See, Valadier, G. "Narrazione artistica dell'operato finora nel restauro dell'Arco di Tito letta nell'Accademia Romana di Archeologia." Rome: Stamperia de Romania, 1822.

↳ Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1800-2018

Notes: The most recent study comprises analysis of the pigments in the bay's reliefs. See: <https://www.yu.edu/cis/activities/arch-of-titus>

↳ Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: No name

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Notes: Although it symbolically commemorates all members of the Flavian dynasty, there is no evidence that suggests this was a place of worship.

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

Notes: This area is densely urbanized, and it was part of the center of the ancient city. There were several important buildings nearby, including various temples dedicated to Jupiter, the Forum of Peace (Templum Pacis), and the Imperial palace (Domus Flavia).

Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– No

Notes: The arch serves as a symbolic gateway between the Roman Forum and the area of the Flavian Amphitheater (Colosseum). In this much, it can be considered as a boundary itself. This is a function common in freestanding arches.

Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– Yes

Notes: The arch functioned as a symbolic gateway that connected several areas of the city, including the Forum, the Palatine hill and the so-called Colosseum Valley. By its placement spanning or besides the Via Sacra, it allowed circulation through these areas.

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

Specify

– Council of elders

– Other [specify]: The Roman Senate

Notes: Many Roman monuments were dedicated by the Senate and the People of Rome (expressed by a number of variations of the formula "SPQR" meaning Senatus Populusque Romanus). In the case of the Arch of Titus, the senatorial dedication might be part of a formulaic process, wherein the living emperor (Domitian) would have also gained prestige while suggesting his own future apotheosis. See fig. 5

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Notes: There were plenty of elite houses on the Palatine hill, the area immediately West of the arch. Another densely populated neighborhood stood to the northeast. The Flavian Imperial palace, built by Domitian, stood on the southeast corner of the Palatine Hill and some see the Arch of Titus as a symbolic gateway for this complex (see, Brinkerhoff, D. "An Immodest Aspect of the Arch of Titus." In *Akten des XIII internationalen Kongresses für klassische Archäologie*, 534-35. Berlin, 1990.)

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

Groups:

- Specialized labourers/craftspeople
- Other [specify]: The Emperor, the Roman Senate, architect(s).

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place created as the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Yes

Specify

- Other [specify]: The death and apotheosis of Titus

Notes: It also commemorates, indirectly, the conquest of Judea in 70 CE and the triumph celebrated in Rome a year later to celebrate the event. The imagery on the inner space of the arch represents the triumph.

Was the creation of the place sponsored by external financial/material donation:

– Yes

Notes: The monument seems to have been financed with the spoils taken by members of the Flavian dynasty (Vespasian [r. 69-79], Titus [r. 79-81], Domitian [r. 81-96]), in the sack of Jerusalem in 70 CE. The parading of the spoils from the great Temple of Jerusalem and scenes of the triumphal procession appear as principal elements in the decoration.

↳ Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:

– No

Notes: There's no proper "donor" but instead it was built with war booty. The monument was presumably financed by the spoils taken from Jerusalem.

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Other [specify]: Strictly speaking, the monument commemorates the death and apotheosis of Titus. However, it also serves as visual propaganda for the role of Titus and the rest of the Flavians in the conquest of Judea in 70 CE.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– Field doesn't know

Sources and Excavations

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by Giuseppe Valadier and Raffaele Stern in the 1820s. See, Valadier, G. "Narrazione artistica dell'operato finora nel restauro dell'Arco di Tito letta nell'Accademia Romana di Archeologia." Rome: Stamperia de Romania, 1822.

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– Official or descriptive name: No name

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Elevation

↳ Type of elevation

– Hill

Notes: The arch stands at the top of the elevation known as the Velia or the Velian Hill, which links the Forum to the West with the Colosseum Valley to the East and the Palatine Hill to the South.

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

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Structures Present

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–Other [specify]: An arch structure spanning a road (Via Sacra)

↳ A group of structures:

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↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

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↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

– Collapsed

Notes: OTHER

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

– For economic reasons

– For political reasons

– Other [specify]: Large parts of the armature and attached decoration were destroyed when the monument was rebuilt as part of a medieval building.

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:

– Human-caused accident

– Natural phenomena

Notes: Possibly also affected by earthquakes, fire, and natural erosion.

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– Periodically

Notes: Most ancient monuments were restored periodically. Arches in particular, have chambers in the attic and elsewhere within the structure to facilitate this process.

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– Renaissance

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: The monument was dedicated in honor of the deified emperor Titus, as expressed in the dedicatory inscription. The apotheosis of Titus is part of the decoration, appearing in the relief on the arch's vault.

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– Field doesn't know

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– Yes

↳ Is it a cenotaph:

– Yes

↳ Body present:

– No

↳ Part of body present:

– No

↳ Does it commemorate a family/clan/group:

– Yes

Notes: Although strictly speaking this is a Senatorial dedication in honor of Titus, the monument also honors Titus' deified father Vespasian and his brother and successor, Domitian. Therefore, it expresses certain dynastic concerns regarding the Flavian clan.

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Notes: Although it symbolically commemorates all members of the Flavian dynasty, there is no evidence that suggests this was a place of worship.

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Council of elders

– Other [specify]: The Roman Senate

Notes: Many Roman monuments were dedicated by the Senate and the People of Rome (expressed by a number of variations of the formula "SPQR" meaning *Senatus Populusque Romanus*). In the case of the Arch of Titus, the senatorial dedication might be part of a formulaic process, wherein the living emperor (Domitian) would have also gained prestige while suggesting his own future apotheosis. See fig. 5

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

↳ Groups:

– Specialized labourers/craftspeople

– Other [specify]: The Emperor, the Roman Senate, architect(s).

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place created as the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

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Was the place created as the result of an event:

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↳ Specify

– Other [specify]: The death and apotheosis of Titus

Notes: It also commemorates, indirectly, the conquest of Judea in 70 CE and the triumph celebrated in Rome a year later to celebrate the event. The imagery on the inner space of the arch represents the triumph.

Was the creation of the place sponsored by external financial/material donation:

– Yes

Notes: The monument seems to have been financed with the spoils taken by members of the Flavian dynasty (Vespasian [r. 69-79], Titus [r. 79-81], Domitian [r. 81-96]), in the sack of Jerusalem in 70 CE. The parading of the spoils from the great Temple of Jerusalem and scenes of the triumphal procession appear as principal elements in the decoration.

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Notes: There's no proper "donor" but instead it was built with war booty. The monument was presumably financed by the spoils taken from Jerusalem.

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– Other [specify]: Strictly speaking, the monument commemorates the death and apotheosis of Titus. However, it also serves as visual propaganda for the role of Titus and the rest of the Flavians in the conquest of Judea in 70 CE.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– Field doesn't know

Design and Material Remains

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– Yes

Notes: Jupiter depicted as an eagle. See Fig. 7

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– Yes

Notes: The frieze incorporates a figure that has been interpreted as the personified River Jordan, which would have functioned as yet another symbol of the conquest of Judea.

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

Notes: These include a personification of Victory, Honos, the Genius of the Roman People and the Genius of the Roman Senate. It is possible that there were others among the lost parts of the decoration and the attic statuary (if there was such).

↳ Supernatural being (abstract)

– Field doesn't know

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– Yes

Notes: With the caveat that it depicts the moment of ascent to heavens, following death, see apotheosis scene in Fig. 7.

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– Yes

Notes: The spoils of the Temple of Jerusalem (Menorah, shewbread table, laws). There were likely also ritual objects associated with Pagan cults in other parts of the decoration.

↳ Humans

– Yes

↳ Supernatural narratives

– Yes

↳ Human narratives

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: Abstract and non-figural decorative elements (cornices, floral friezes, column capitals, etc.)

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– No

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

Notes: The decoration of the monument includes: 2 relief panels on the inside of the bay (see figs. 2 and 3). A frieze depicting a triumphal procession (see fig. 7), depictions of Victories on the spandrels, various architectural elements such as column capitals, cornices, and friezes, the dedicatory inscription, and possibly a group of gilded bronze statues crowning the structure (nothing remains of this). Besides the possibility of (lost)

attic statuary, there appear to be portions of decoration that did not survive the Medieval modifications of the structure.

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

Notes: If we consider "inside" as the bay passage. There's no decoration on the actual chambers inside the structure.

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

Notes: Most likely the monument contained a group of statues on the attic. There's no surviving physical remains of this, and the literature is vague. Mart. Spect. 2.1-4, notes the presence of scaffolding in the Via Appia, which could have been related to the arch's construction. In the sixth century, Cassiodorus calls for restoration of bronze elephants that had fallen on the road; these might have decorated the arch or a similar monument. Cassiod. Var. 10.30.1.

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Titus deified and Jupiter represented as an eagle.

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

Notes: The reliefs on the inside of the bay include personifications such as Honos, Virtus (possibly), the Genius of the Roman Senate and the Genius of the Roman People. Two flying Victories appear on the spandrels on both facades (see figs. 2, 3, 8).

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

Notes: The reliefs on the inside of the bay depict two scenes of a triumphal procession. On the north relief, there's Titus riding a chariot pulled by horses and surrounded by lictors (bodyguards). On the south relief, a series of men and lictors carry biers with de spoils of Jerusalem. See figs. 2 and 3.

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

Notes: There are 4 horses pulling the triumphal chariot, an eagle as symbol of Jupiter, presumably more horses on the statuary group on the attic, and animals dedicated to sacrifices depicted on the frieze (see Fig. 8).

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Not all parts of the decoration survives, so this is unknown.

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

Notes: Floral motifs, coffers inside the vault, architectural ornament in the entablature, column capitals, etc.

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

Notes: Various floral friezes appear on the intrados of the arch.

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– Yes

Notes: The dedicatory inscription, composed of large gilded bronze letters, was surely part of the decoration. See Fig. 5.

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: Presumably the color of marble elements functioned as a form of decoration.

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there statues present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Presumably there were statues on top of the attic, but there's no direct evidence for this.

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief—as opposed to sculpture carved on the round—is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

— Yes

↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

— Yes

Notes: These include the relief inside the bay where Titus rides the triumphal chariot (see Fig. 2), and the vault scene depicting the apotheosis of Titus (see Fig. 7).

↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:

— Yes

Notes: The moment of apotheosis depicted on the vault relief (see Fig. 7) could be considered a mythological narrative.

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:

— Yes

Notes: The reliefs inside the bay represent a symbolic narration of the triumph celebrated in Rome in 71 CE by Vespasian and Titus, commemorating the victory over Judea. For information on this triumph, see especially Book 7 of Josephus' *Bellum Judaicum*.

↳ Other [Specify]

— Other [specify]: Frieze

Notes: The frieze is a common feature in triumphal/honorific arches. It was carved circling around the structure, right below the cornice and represents a triumphal procession.

↳ Are there paintings present:

— Yes

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

— Field doesn't know

Notes: Probably not.

↳ Are they wall paintings:

— No

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

— Field doesn't know

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– Yes

Notes: Paint was applied to the existing reliefs.

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Evidence of pigments

Notes: A recent study analyzed traces of pigment that survive in the reliefs:

<https://www.yu.edu/cis/activities/arch-of-titus>

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– Yes

Notes: The inscription's primary function was arguably declarative, but studies suggest the gilded bronze letters also had a decorative purpose.

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative

[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

Notes: See Fig. 5

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: NA

↳ Other type of decoration:

–Yes [specify]: Architectural elements such as column shafts and cornices

Notes: These were generally highly ornate. One must consider also the natural polychromy of

marble elements as a decorative aspect of the monument.

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:

– Percentage: 70

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– Square meters: 90

Notes: Approximate in meters (question really doesn't apply)

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 14.44

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Square meters: 90

Notes: Again, question not precisely relevant.

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 14.44

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– No

↳ Sand

– No

↳ Clay

– No

↳ Plaster

– No

↳ Wood

– No

↳ Grass

– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– No

Notes: Pentelic marble from Greece was used in the rest and most of the structure.

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– Yes

Notes: Pentelic marble comes from Mount Pentelicus in Greece (near Athens). It was one of the most favored types of marble employed in Roman monuments.

↳ Other

– No

– Yes

↳ Earth

– No

↳ Sand

– No

↳ Clay

– No

↳ Plaster
– No

↳ Wood
– No

↳ Grass
– No

↳ Stone
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

Notes: Luna marble from Italy (modern Carrara) was used for the attic of the structure.

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Other
– Yes [specify]: Pigments

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: Carved stone, pigment, gilded letters (inscription), possibly gilded bronze statuary on the attic.

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– No

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:
– Percentage: 70

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:
– Square meters: 90
Notes: Approximate in meters (question really doesn't apply)

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:
– Height, meters: 14.44

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:
– Square meters: 90
Notes: Again, question not precisely relevant.

↳ Height of average monument, meters:
– Height, meters: 14.44

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth
– No

↳ Sand
– No

↳ Clay
– No

↳ Plaster
– No

↳ Wood
– No

↳ Grass
– No

↳ Stone
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– No

Notes: Pentelic marble from Greece was used in the rest and most of the structure.

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– Yes

Notes: Pentelic marble comes from Mount Pentelicus in Greece (near Athens). It was one of the most favored types of marble employed in Roman monuments.

↳ Other
– No

– Yes

↳ Earth
– No

↳ Sand
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↳ Clay
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↳ Plaster
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↳ Wood
– No

↳ Grass
– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

Notes: Luna marble from Italy (modern Carrara) was used for the attic of the structure.

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Other

– Yes [specify]: Pigments

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: Carved stone, pigment, gilded letters (inscription), possibly gilded bronze statuary on the attic.

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

Notes: The decoration of the monument includes: 2 relief panels on the inside of the bay (see figs. 2 and 3). A frieze depicting a triumphal procession (see fig. 7), depictions of Victories on the spandrels, various architectural elements such as column capitals, cornices, and friezes, the dedicatory inscription, and possibly a group of gilded bronze statues crowning the structure (nothing remains of this). Besides the possibility of (lost) attic statuary, there appear to be portions of decoration that did not survive the Medieval modifications of the structure.

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

Notes: If we consider "inside" as the bay passage. There's no decoration on the actual chambers inside the structure.

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

Notes: Most likely the monument contained a group of statues on the attic. There's no surviving physical remains of this, and the literature is vague. Mart. Spect. 2.1-4, notes the presence of scaffolding in the Via Appia, which could have been related to the arch's construction. In the sixth century, Cassiodorus calls for restoration of bronze elephants than had fallen on the road; these might have decorated the arch or a similar monument. Cassiod. Var. 10.30.1.

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Titus deified and Jupiter represented as an eagle.

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

Notes: The reliefs on the inside of the bay include personifications such as Honos, Virtus (possibly), the Genius of the Roman Senate and the Genius of the Roman People. Two flying Victories appear on the spandrels on both facades (see figs. 2, 3, 8).

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

Notes: The reliefs on the inside of the bay depict two scenes of a triumphal procession. On the north relief, there's Titus riding a chariot pulled by horses and surrounded by lictors (bodyguards). On the south relief, a series of men and lictors carry biers with de spoils of Jerusalem. See figs. 2 and 3.

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

Notes: There are 4 horses pulling the triumphal chariot, an eagle as symbol of Jupiter, presumably more horses on the statuary group on the attic, and animals dedicated to sacrifices depicted on the frieze (see Fig. 8).

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Not all parts of the decoration survives, so this is unknown.

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

Notes: Floral motifs, coffered inside the vault, architectural ornament in the entablature, column capitals, etc.

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

Notes: Various floral friezes appear on the intrados of the arch.

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– Yes

Notes: The dedicatory inscription, composed of large gilded bronze letters, was surely part of the decoration. See Fig. 5.

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: Presumably the color of marble elements functioned as a form of decoration.

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there statues present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Presumably there were statues on top of the attic, but there's no direct evidence for this.

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief—as opposed to sculpture carved on the round—is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– Yes

Notes: These include the relief inside the bay where Titus rides the triumphal chariot (see Fig. 2), and the vault scene depicting the apotheosis of Titus (see Fig. 7).

↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:

– Yes

Notes: The moment of apotheosis depicted on the vault relief (see Fig. 7) could be considered a mythological narrative.

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

Notes: The reliefs inside the bay represent a symbolic narration of the triumph celebrated in Rome in 71 CE by Vespasian and Titus, commemorating the victory over Judea. For information on this triumph, see especially Book 7 of Josephus' *Bellum Judaicum*.

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: Frieze

Notes: The frieze is a common feature in triumphal/honorific arches. It was carved circling around the structure, right below the cornice and represents a triumphal procession.

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Probably not.

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– No

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– Yes

Notes: Paint was applied to the existing reliefs.

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Evidence of pigments

Notes: A recent study analyzed traces of pigment that survive in the reliefs:
<https://www.yu.edu/cis/activities/arch-of-titus>

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– Yes

Notes: The inscription's primary function was arguably declarative, but studies suggest the gilded bronze letters also had a decorative purpose.

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative

[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

Notes: See Fig. 5

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: NA

↳ Other type of decoration:

–Yes [specify]: Architectural elements such as column shafts and cornices

Notes: These were generally highly ornate. One must consider also the natural polychromy of marble elements as a decorative aspect of the monument.

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– Yes

Notes: Jupiter depicted as an eagle. See Fig. 7

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– Yes

Notes: The frieze incorporates a figure that has been interpreted as the personified River Jordan, which would have functioned as yet another symbol of the conquest of Judea.

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

Notes: These include a personification of Victory, Honos, the Genius of the Roman People and the Genius of the Roman Senate. It is possible that there were others among the lost parts of the decoration and the attic statuary (if there was such).

↳ Supernatural being (abstract)

– Field doesn't know

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– Yes

Notes: With the caveat that it depicts the moment of ascent to heavens, following death, see apotheosis scene in Fig. 7.

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– Yes

Notes: The spoils of the Temple of Jerusalem (Menorah, shewbread table, laws). There were likely also ritual objects associated with Pagan cults in other parts of the decoration.

↳ Humans

– Yes

↳ Supernatural narratives

– Yes

↳ Human narratives

– Yes

Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Abstract and non-figural decorative elements (cornices, floral friezes, column capitals, etc.)

Beliefs and Practices

Is divination present:

– Field doesn't know

Do rituals occur at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is likely that sacrifices were performed at various moments during the vowing, construction, and dedication of the structure.

Are pilgrimages present:

– Field doesn't know

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Field doesn't know

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Are they anthropomorphic:

– No

Notes: I'm referring here to Jupiter, who appears in the form of an eagle taking Titus in apotheosis.

Are they sky deity:

– Yes

↳ Are they cthonic (underworld)

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– Yes

Notes: In a way, the apotheosis of the emperor was a form of aligning with the high god (Jupiter)

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– Yes

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– Yes

Notes: Divine sanction?

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Probably not. Jupiter was seen in mythology as possessing weaknesses similar to those of humans. In general, deities in the Greco-Roman pantheon were highly anthropomorphized.

↳ Are they other:

–Other [specify]: Possibly others

Notes: Among the parts of the decoration lost, there were likely depictions of more high gods of the Greco-Roman pantheon

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Yes

Notes: There were public feasts as part of triumphal processions. Given that this arch possibly served as stage for various such processions in the centuries after its construction, it is likely that parts of public feasts happened around the structure. This is purely speculative.

↳ Is feasting connected to the worship/sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

↳ Is feasting sponsored by the same entity that built/maintains the place:

– Yes

↳ Priests
– Field doesn't know

↳ Local elites
– Yes

Notes: Public magistrates in charge of the maintenance of monuments (aediles, etc.)

↳ Private contributions
– Field doesn't know

↳ Other
–Other [specify]: na

↳ Does feasting occur in a specific location with the place:
– Field doesn't know

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Does the supreme high god communicates with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:

– Yes

Notes: If by communication we understand interacting visually and physically with the monument and its imagery.

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: If Titus is considered a god in this stage.

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Although it served as a cenotaph for Titus, we don't know if worship actually occurred at the site.

It was likely just a memorial for the deceased emperor and the Judaic triumph.

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are festivals present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Because of the location of this monument, it is very likely that it participated in some way in the many festivals occurring in the city of Rome.

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Field doesn't know

Are previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Human spirits can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: Not actually seen, but in the form of reliefs.

Human spritis can be phyiscally felt:

– Field doesn't know

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Field doesn't know

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There might have been animal sacrifices during the official dedication of the monument, but we don't have direct evidence for this.

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

Notes: Although not strictly defined as grave goods, the materials and processes associated with this structure might be considered as funerary offerings. In fact, the structure itself likely served this purpose.

↳ Personal effects:

– No

↳ Valuable/precious items:

– Yes

↳ Significant value:

Gold, jade, intensely worked objects, or meaningful symbolid value

– Yes

Notes: If we consider architecture as a valuable object. Additionally, the materials of construction--imported and local marble, bronze, and gold--were highly prized.

↳ Some value, valuable or useful objects:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: na

↳ Other

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– Yes

↳ Human spritis can be phyiscally felt:

– Field doesn't know

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance)

– Yes

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff

– Yes

Notes: Possibly slaves and employees working for the city's aediles (magistrates in charge of public spaces and monuments)

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: na

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Are formal burials present:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings are present:

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine spirits can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: In this context, Titus can be considered a mixed human-divine spirit, since he is depicted in a liminal state, in transition from life to death and from mortality to immortality.

↳ Mixed human-divine spirits can be physically felt:

– Field doesn't know

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Although it served as a cenotaph for Titus, we don't know if worship actually occurred at the site. It was likely just a memorial for the deceased emperor and the Judaic triumph.

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There might have been animal sacrifices during the official dedication of the monument, but we don't have direct evidence for this.

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

Notes: Although not strictly defined as grave goods, the materials and processes associated with this structure might be considered as funerary offerings. In fact, the structure itself likely served this purpose.

↳ Personal effects:

– No

↳ Valuable/precious items:

– Yes

↳ Significant value:

Gold, jade, intensely worked objects, or meaningful symbolid value

– Yes

Notes: If we consider architecture as a valuable object. Additionally, the materials of construction--imported and local marble, bronze, and gold--were highly prized.

↳ Some value, valuable or useful objects:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: na

↳ Other

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– No

Notes: I'm referring here to Jupiter, who appears in the form of an eagle taking Titus in apotheosis.

↳ Are they sky deity:

– Yes

↳ Are they cthonic (underworld)

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– Yes

Notes: In a way, the apotheosis of the emperor was a form of aligning with the high god (Jupiter)

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:
– Yes

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:
– No

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:
– Yes
Notes: Divine sanction?

↳ Are they unquestionably good:
– Field doesn't know
Notes: Probably not. Jupiter was seen in mythology as possessing weaknesses similar to those of humans. In general, deities in the Greco-Roman pantheon were highly anthropomorphized.

↳ Are they other:
– Other [specify]: Possibly others
Notes: Among the parts of the decoration lost, there were likely depictions of more high gods of the Greco-Roman pantheon

Does the supreme high god communicates with the living at this place:
– Field doesn't know

Are previously human spirits are present:
– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen:
– Yes
Notes: Not actually seen, but in the form of reliefs.

↳ Human spritis can be phyiscally felt:
– Field doesn't know

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:
– Field doesn't know

Are nonhuman supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– Field doesn't know

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine spirits can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: In this context, Titus can be considered a mixed human-divine spirit, since he is depicted in a liminal state, in transition from life to death and from mortality to immortality.

↳ Mixed human-divine spirits can be physically felt:

– Field doesn't know

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Field doesn't know

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:

– Yes

Notes: If by communication we understand interacting visually and physically with the monument and its imagery.

Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: If Titus is considered a god in this stage.

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is likely that sacrifices were performed at various moments during the vowing, construction, and dedication of the structure.

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Field doesn't know

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Field doesn't know

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

Is it required:

– Field doesn't know

Is there cleansing (for the maintenance)

– Yes

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff

– Yes

Notes: Possibly slaves and employees working for the city's aediles (magistrates in charge of public spaces and monuments)

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: na

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Field doesn't know

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Yes

Notes: There were public feasts as part of triumphal processions. Given that this arch possibly served as stage for various such processions in the centuries after its construction, it is likely that parts of public feasts happened around the structure. This is purely speculative.

↳ Is feasting connected to the worship/sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

↳ Is feasting sponsored by the same entity that built/maintains the place:

– Yes

↳ Priests

– Field doesn't know

↳ Local elites

– Yes

Notes: Public magistrates in charge of the maintenance of monuments (aediles, etc.)

↳ Private contributions

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: na

Does feasting occur in a specific location with the place:

– Field doesn't know

Are festivals present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Because of the location of this monument, it is very likely that it participated in some way in the many festivals occurring in the city of Rome.

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– Field doesn't know

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Institutions and Scriptures

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There was presumably an established cult with priests and attendants for deified emperors, but there is no direct evidence of this for Titus or his Arch

Are there scriptures associated with this place

– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– No

Is this palce used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders)

– Yes

Notes: There were people in charge of the maintenance of public monuments, but they were no necessarily religious specialists

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals who's primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintaince of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There was presumably an established cult with priests and attendants for deified emperors, but there is no direct evidence of this for Titus or his Arch

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Is this palce used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders)

– Yes

Notes: There were people in charge of the maintenance of public monuments, but they were no

necessarily religious specialists

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place

– No